

Awareness and Utilisation of Cloud Computing Technologies for Library Services: A Survey of Librarians in Colleges of Education Libraries in Nigeria

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Abstract

Purpose of the Study: *The study's purpose is to investigate the cloud computing technologies used by librarians and report on the concerns related to implementing cloud-completion technologies in selected colleges of education libraries in Nigeria.*

Methodology: *Data was collected from 116 para-professional and professional librarians working in 11 selected Federal Colleges of education in Nigeria.*

Findings: *The results of the study show that YouTube, Google Drive, OneDrive, Gmail, and Google Scholar are the commonly used cloud computing technologies by librarians in colleges of education libraries in Nigeria. The study also found that librarians' purpose in using cloud computing technologies is to store and share files, share videos related to library orientations/other video content, and collaborate with other librarians for research projects. The study also found that adopting cloud computing technologies has advantages such as storage capacity, access to files from anywhere, better performance, data security, software updates automatically, and lower maintenance costs. The findings will inform librarians or information professionals about the role played by cloud computing in developing information services and how to use it.*

Recommendations/Conclusion: *The study concludes by providing a better understanding and application of cloud computing to advance the provision of library services to users of college libraries and other libraries worldwide.*

Study Type: *Research paper*

Keywords: Cloud computing technologies, college libraries, librarians, Nigeria.

Introduction

Nowadays, the library environment is developing considerably, given the significant development of information and communications technology (ICT), and in the context of lack of financial resources and budget weakness, there is an increasing need to take advantage of cloud computing applications in the field of libraries to improve services. Over time, libraries have operated manually to deliver services to their clientele. This method had major drawbacks, such as delay, low productivity, data loss, and staff turnover (Sharma, Gupta & Acharya, 2021). Cloud computing has emerged as a practical and optimal solution after the provision of Internet infrastructure in various parts of the world. Cloud storage has become one of the most convenient and efficient methods to store data online. Cloud computing can be defined as a technology that relies on the transfer of processing and storage space of a computer to the so-called cloud that is accessed via the Internet (Elshite, 2013). In a cloud computing environment, processes and applications run in the cloud and do not require processing power or hard disk space like the traditional desktop software (Elshite, 2013).

Some of the cloud computing technologies are YouTube, Google Drive, OPAC, Google Form, OneDrive, Gmail, Google Scholar, and so on. According to Badawi and Kayed (2015), “Information and communication technology (ICT) development has brought a dramatic change in every sector, and libraries are not an exception to it”. Cloud computing offers an application service framework that can integrate all libraries’ digital information resources and process distributed digital resources, information integration, and reconfiguration to better meet user library services needs where the digital book services have become an academic hub for disseminating and processing modern human knowledge (Lijuan, 2020). Cloud computing is the result of advancements in various technologies, including the Internet, hardware, systems management and distributed computing (Buyya et al., 2011). In Nigeria, even though cloud computing is internationally being adopted, some libraries still operate on the traditional ICT-based desktop applications that are installed on the servers and virtualised on the library network for access. Notable with these technologies is that they are costly when considering purchases, computer and server maintenance, and software upgrades. Ugwoke and Okafor (2017) explained that libraries operating on the traditional library model are overcrowded with several challenges such as poor access time, distance barrier, high expenses and other materials, which make them inconvenient for mobility. The lack of cloud computing in libraries limits both librarians and library users from having remote access to the library system, services and applications because desktop applications are confined to a physical location. Consequently, this limits libraries from providing effective and efficient library services because desktop applications do not make it convenient for libraries to provide users with remote access (Soniya & Senthil, 2015). To overcome this problem, many libraries have adopted the use of cloud computing (Sahu, 2015; Njoku & Ken-Agbirio, 2021). According to Sahu (2015; p.213), “Cloud computing has become a new catchword in the field of libraries, which enables them to run different ICT services without problems”. Compared to traditional ICT, cloud computing is relatively cheaper to run libraries and Information Services (LIS) because of its on-demand computing service, which provides pay-per-usage opportunities for the application of cloud-based services such as interlibrary loans and online references (Shaw, 2013). However, Wada (2018) noted that “many people hardly notice that cloud computing is part of their daily activities until people are engaged in carrying out their transactions in the cloud, such as emailing.”

Academic libraries are using new and emerging technologies such as cloud computing, social media, and others to expand services, thereby adding more value to their services, making them attractive to the users and focusing on maximising the effectiveness of shared resources for libraries to deliver library services. The impact of technological innovations has evaded the processes and services, creating new demand and service orientation, meaning academic libraries and their traditional services must evolve to meet the current expectations (Irenea et al., 2019). Libraries adopt cloud computing to advance library services, such as making use of cloud computing to allow patrons to have remote access to the library collections. Cloud computing provides new opportunities for innovation and offers unprecedented levels of configurability for diverse groups of users, of which the library is not left out (Irenea et al., 2018). Studies have found that readiness for cloud adoption is low in developing countries like Nigeria despite its benefits and solutions to challenges such as electricity consumption, capital investment network provision, and so on (de Bruin & Floridi, 2016; Arkorful, 2019). To the best of the researcher’s knowledge, no study has been conducted on cloud technology adoption in colleges of education libraries in Nigeria. The importance of cloud computing and its potential, and the possibility of using them in the provision of multiple services, including the provision of electronic services in libraries, pushed the researchers to fill the gap by investigating the level of awareness and use of cloud computing technologies to render library services in selected Colleges of Education in Nigeria. To achieve this, the following research questions were raised to guide the study:

Research Questions

1. What type of cloud computing technologies are being used by the librarians in the selected College libraries in Nigeria?
2. What level of librarians' computer literacy skills are required to use cloud computing technologies?
3. What are the purposes for which librarians in the selected college libraries in Nigeria use cloud computing technologies?
4. What are the benefits of adopting cloud computing to render library services?
5. What challenges do librarians in selected college libraries in Nigeria experience in adopting cloud computing technologies?

Literature review

Cloud computing applications in libraries

Cloud computing can be defined as a technology that relies on the transfer of processing and storage space of a computer to the so-called cloud that is accessed via the Internet (Elshite, 2013). Cloud computing enables organisations to deliver support applications and avoid the need to develop their IT systems (Feuerlicht et al., 2010). In cloud storage, the user, rather than saving the data at local storage or hard disk, stores data somewhere at a remote location, which can be accessed using an internet service (Sharma, Gupta & Acharya, 2021). Various cloud storage service providers sell storage services for different ranges. Njoku and Ken-Agbiriogu (2021) investigated awareness and use of cloud computing and its implications by libraries in selected academic libraries in Imo State, Nigeria. The study revealed that there is a certain level of awareness of cloud computing technologies and models in the libraries studied. It was also discovered that libraries in the institutions used cloud computing technology studied, and economy of resource cost-effectiveness and file sharing are some of the major positive implications of librarians' adoption of cloud computing technologies. However, security, privacy, and multiple taxation were also identified as major negative implications of librarians' adoption of cloud computing when discharging their functions in libraries. Arkorful (2019) also studied cloud computing adoption in public and private universities in Sub-Saharan Africa and reported that despite the potential benefits that are associated with cloud computing, which include reduction of total costs of acquisition or ownership of hardware, software and skilled resources, the adoption level of cloud services is still very low in higher institutions of learning in Africa due to security issues, especially trust issues which remain a major concern over cloud solutions.

In this era, libraries are changing almost by using cloud computing technology. Libraries use cloud-based resources primarily to create digital libraries, social networking, and knowledge communication without discarding concerns about cloud-related issues like privacy, protection, etc. Therefore, libraries need to think deeply about library services with cloud-based technology to provide their customers with sincere service. Several years ago, libraries used many cloud computing-based applications such as email. Still, it is clear that cloud computing has developed rapidly into a model of data storage and exchange, and it also helps save money and time and simplifies workflow (Jalamneh & Khder, 2021). Cloud computing technology services can be widely divided into three types (Ogbu & Lawal, 2013): Infrastructure as a service, Platform as a service, and Software as a service.

1. Infrastructure as a service: the basic layer of cloud computing.
2. Platform as a service: Environmental computing or platform services are the next level of the cloud. They are often used by organisations that develop or amend applications for their programs. Environmental computing supports program development operations, including prototypes, development, testing, publishing and hosting programs. The cloud services platform is usually prearranged with a particular operating environment, such as Windows or Linux.
3. Software as a service is the highest level of cloud, as software apps or library data are hosted online. This level of cloud is the easiest for non-profit organisations and libraries to access. Still, it requires development and relatively little organisational training to get and operate.

An exploratory study by Noa (2015) focused on factors influencing librarians' application of cloud computing. The study found that the behavioural goal of adopting cloud computing was impacted by personal innovativeness and perceived ease of use. Similarly, Amponsah, Panford and Hayfron-Acquah (2016) determined factors influencing cloud computing adoption in a developing country, Ghana. The findings discovered that habit, facilitating condition, price value and performance expectancy were positive significant factors influencing the implementation of cloud computing in Ghana. Yaseen et al. (2022) assessed the factors that influence cloud computing adoption among small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in Jordan. The results indicate that seven factors significantly affect cloud computing adoption among SMEs. Among these factors, cost reduction was found to be the strongest predictor, while the weakest predictor was firm size. Muhammed et al. (2017) highlight major challenges in the adoption of cloud computing, which include poor Internet service, power supply, fear of hackers and insecurity. The study by Amponsah, Panford and Hayfron-Acquah (2016) determined factors influencing cloud computing adoption in the developing country of Ghana and found that insignificant security, hedonic motivation, effort expectancy and social influence negatively influence cloud computing application in Ghana.

Benefits of adopting cloud computing in the library

Cloud computing has emerged as a big benefit for libraries, giving libraries multiple ways to link their resources to cloud computing (Irenea et al., 2018; Mahajan & Gulati, 2017). Cloud computing is a platform solution for handling all library systems, including circulation, cataloguing, acquisitions, serials, wireless access points, digital tools, internet connectivity, thin client architecture, system data analytics and digital librarians (Lijuan, 2020). Due to the growth of cloud computing use, the question arises as to what factors may influence information professionals to adopt new technologies, such as cloud computing, in their libraries. Libraries worldwide have also started using cloud computing to handle e-resources usage, hosting web applications, cataloguing online public access, managing digital libraries, hosting various statistical tools and data sets, etc. (Tripathi & Pandey, 2019). Cloud computing has had a huge influence on libraries. This technology has provided an opportunity for libraries to overcome the fear of data loss and massive costs in building infrastructure, leading to highly scalable, service-oriented architecture and many other things (Vishakha & Sarangapani, 2019). The most remarkable benefit is online repositories and global access to services. Although implementation is a bit costly, libraries move slowly towards cloud computing and are undoubtedly viewed in libraries as a boon in the digital age. Key factors for cloud adoption include strengthening student-teacher interactions through collaboration resources and proposing cloud applications for mobile devices to access various learning materials virtually and secure off-campus email (Ali, 2021).

Cloud computing helps library and information science (LIS) professionals build an ecosystem to make library services convenient for their users (Muhammad, 2019). We need to develop these kinds of libraries due to knowledge explosion, difficulties accessing information, saving user and staff time, resource sharing and resource management issues, and the most important reason is cost-effectiveness (Srinivas, 2017). E-resources, which are an academic library demand, and database sharing are possible using cloud services; OCLC is one of its co-web examples, OPAC, and can be uploaded to the cloud. It offers online cataloguing resources (Kaur, 2018). Cloud computing, according to Jalamneh and Khder (2021), is characterised by the following:

Low-cost PCs for beneficiaries: There is no need to purchase powerful and expensive cloud equipment to utilise cloud computing, which involves processes and applications running in the cloud and does not require processing power or hard disk space like traditional desktop software.

Better performance: Because programs or files are not loaded on local personal computers, beneficiaries are not subject to delays due to the operation or closure of personal computers. Thanks to the absence of any internal traffic, the internal network will become much faster.

Lower maintenance costs: Organizations' hardware and software maintenance costs will be much lower, no matter how much hardware and software the company has available. This will require fewer servers for IT staff.

Low software costs: There is no need to purchase software packages for all computers in the organisation, but employees who already use applications need to access these applications in the cloud

Software update automatically: There are no additional expenses required to update or upgrade programs for organisations.

Unlimited storage capacity: The cloud provides unlimited virtual storage capacity, which can be increased at any time for a small additional charge.

Increased data security: All data is stored in the cloud, which encourages users not to worry about disk loss or disasters in the office and elsewhere.

Access to files from anywhere: With the cloud, there is no need to take documents, as the PC can be accessed from anywhere with access to the Internet.

Challenges to implementing cloud computing technologies

Cloud storage is the library's latest technology, where the end-user can conveniently access the library at remote locations. However, using or implementing this technology library faces many issues, such as security and data privacy. One major task of LIS professionals in this digital era is to make cloud-based platforms secure for delivering library services to users. Bhardwaj (2018) and Ali (2021) examine cloud computing adoption efficiency and risks in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) from several perceptions. Looking at cloud quality and threats through a multi-perception lens. The findings indicate that trust, protection and privacy are the main factors of non-adoption, as stakeholders believe that cloud computing cannot completely ensure sensitive information protection. According to Shiferaw and Cerna (2016), before turning to a cloud computing environment, it is necessary to identify the security risks of the cloud, that is, to ensure the certificates for data security protection and storage location and its safe coding.

Jalamneh and Khder (2021) studied the challenges of implementing cloud computing in the Arab library environment. They concluded that the main challenges lie in professionalism, training and technical

difficulties, such as the availability of applications and programs, storage capacity, huge volume of data, privacy and information security. Onu, Okorie and Onwubiko (2019) aver that the challenges of cloud computing in library and information services are embedded in its demerits. The security of library resources in the cloud environment is a serious concern. Entrusting cloud service providers with library resources may, in the end, jeopardise library programmes and services. The challenge posed by the issue of the epileptic and erratic nature of power supply from the national grid should not be swept under the carpet while considering the demand for providing cloud computing services by libraries, as cloud computing is based online with effective bandwidths and internet connectivity. It requires prompt, fast, dedicated and reliable internet connectivity at all times. Potnis, Regenstreif-Harms, and Hunter (2018) examined the challenges of using cloud computing to deploy library services, what data issues can influence IT, the users, the costs, and the challenges of policy. The study concluded that there are seven main critical areas to ensure a successful deployment of Software as a Service (SaaS) in libraries with relation to data, authentication and privacy of patrons, skills and knowledge of library staff and organisational culture, IT infrastructure, features of services, fixed and operational costs associated with data and technology, and policies and contracts.

Methodology

The study covered all professionals and para-professional librarians working in selected Colleges of Education libraries in Nigeria. The questionnaire was designed to collect data from the librarians in 11 colleges of education owned by the federal government and the states of Nigeria. The researchers, with the help of other research assistants, visited the various selected colleges of education libraries in Nigeria to distribute the questionnaire designed for the study. Most of the items on the instrument, such as benefits and concerns related to adopting cloud computing technologies, are open-ended questions designed to collect qualitative data from respondents. Completed and returned copies of the questionnaire were used for the analysis. The quantitative data collected was analysed by a statistician using SPSS software, and qualitative data was collected using the content analysis method, where similar topics were brought together.

Results

In total, 116 professional and para-professional librarians working in 11 State and Federal Colleges of education libraries responded to the study. Table 1 provides a breakdown of the number of respondents in each institution.

Table 1: No of respondents in selected Federal and State colleges of Education in Nigeria.

s/n	Name of university	Date Established	State	No of respondents
1	College of Education, Ekiadolor	1980	Edo State	12
2	Federal College of Education, Obudu	1983	Cross River State	13
3	Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba	1987	Delta state	11

4	Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku	1989	Rivers State	14
5	Akwa Ibom State College of Education	1991	Akwa Ibom State	12
6	College of Education Warri	1999	Delta State	12
7	Ebonyi State College of Education	2001	Ebonyi State	10
8	Delta State College of Education, Mosogar.	2005	Delta State	3
9	College of Education, Akemkpa	2008	Cross River State	13
10	Isaac Jasper Boro College of Education	2012	Bayelsa state	7
11	Edo State College of Education	2020	Edo State	9
	Total			116

Staff designation

Respondents were asked to provide information about their current designations. The largest category of staff who responded to the survey were assistant librarians (39: 33.6%), followed by library officers (34: 29.3%) and senior librarians (22: 19.0%) (see details in Table 2).

Table 2: Staff designation

Staff designation	No of respondents	(%)
College Librarian	3	2.6
Principal Librarian	5	4.3
Senior Librarian	22	19.0
Assistant Librarian	39	33.6
Chief Library Officer	13	11.2
Library Officer	34	29.3
Total	116	100%

Gender distribution of respondents

Out of the 116 respondents, 68 (58.6%) indicated as females, while 48 (41.4%) indicated as males.

Cloud computing technologies used by librarians in the selected Colleges of Education libraries in Nigeria.

The respondents were asked to mention some cloud computing technologies they used in their libraries in an open-ended question. The responses to this question were sorted and grouped into similar cloud computing technologies. The results show that YouTube (112: 96.6%), Google Drive (102: 87.9%), OneDrive (98: 84.5%), Gmail (92: 79.3%), and Google Scholar (88: 75.9%) are the most mentioned cloud computing technologies used by the librarians in selected colleges of education libraries in Nigeria (Details in Table 3).

Table 3: Cloud computing technologies used by librarians in colleges of education libraries.

cloud computing technologies used	No of responses	Percentage
YouTube	112	96.6%
Google Drive	102	87.9%
OneDrive	98	84.5%
Gmail	92	79.3%
Google Scholar	88	75.9%
Google Form	87	75.0%
Dropbox	72	62.1%
iCloud	71	61.2%
OPAC	63	54.3%
Sync.com	47	40.5%
Amazon Cloud	33	28.4%

Level of computer literacy skills to use cloud computing technologies.

The reason for adding this question was because computer literacy skills are needed to effectively use cloud computing technologies. For that reason, respondents were asked to rate their level of computer literacy skills to use cloud computing technologies. Almost half (56: 48.3%) of the respondents rated their computer literacy skills to use cloud computing to be very good, followed by those who rated their computer literacy skills to use cloud computing technologies to be excellent (27: 23.3%), and 19 (16.4%) respondents rated their computer literacy skills to be good. Meanwhile, 12 (10.3%) respondents rated their skills in using cloud computing technologies as poor, and 2 (1.7%) respondents rated their skills as very poor (Table 4).

Table 4: Level of computer literacy skills to use cloud computing technologies

Level of skills	No of respondents	(%)
Very good	56	48.3%
Excellent	27	23.3%
Good	19	16.4%
Poor	12	10.3%
Very poor	2	1.7%
Total	116	100%

Purpose of using cloud computing technologies by the librarians in selected Colleges of Education libraries.

Topics listed the qualitative data collected, and then the responses were finally grouped into similar categories and ranked in order.

The most commonly mentioned purpose of librarians' use of cloud computing technologies is to store and share files, and 98 (98.5%) respondents cited it. Closely followed by 82 (70.7%) respondents who mentioned using cloud computing technologies for sharing videos related to library orientations/other video contents, and 79 (68.1%) respondents mentioned using cloud computing technologies to collaborate with other librarians for research projects (Table 5).

Table 5: Purpose of using cloud computing technologies by the librarians in selected Colleges of Education libraries in Nigeria.

Categories	No. of responses	Order	%
Use to store and share files	98	1 st	98.5%
Sharing videos (library orientations/other video content)	82	2 nd	70.7%
To collaborate with other librarians for research projects	79	3 rd	68.1%
Survey users' level of satisfaction with library services	75	4 th	64.7%
Online document editing services	62	5 th	53.4%
Provision of virtual/online reference	59	6 th	50.9%
Information collection services	57	7 th	49.1%

Use to download bibliographic descriptive records	52	8 th	44.8%
Library awareness campaign services	46	9 th	39.7%
For searching current publications	44	10 th	37.9%
Library meetings and activities	41	11 th	35.3%

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The benefits of adopting cloud computing to render library services.

Topics listed the qualitative data collected, and then the responses were finally grouped into similar categories and ranked in order. The results revealed that out of the 116 respondents, storage capacity was the most mentioned and 107 (92.2%) respondents mentioned it. This was followed by access to files from anywhere mentioned by 99 (85.3%) and better performance mentioned by 87 (75%) respondents. Others are: data security, mentioned by 84 (72.4%) respondents; software update automatically, mentioned by 79 (68%) respondents; and lower maintenance costs, mentioned by 73 (62.9%) respondents (Table 6). The results show that adopting cloud computing technologies has advantages such as storage capacity, access to files from anywhere, better performance, data security, software updates automatically, and lower maintenance costs.

Table 6: Benefits of adopting cloud computing to render library services

Categories	No. of responses	order	%
Storage capacity	107	1st	92.2%
Access to files from anywhere	99	2nd	85.3%
Better performance	87	3rd	75%
Data security	84	3th	72.4%
Software update automatically	79	5th	68%
Lower maintenance costs	73	6th	62.9%

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Concerns associated with adopting cloud computing technologies.

Respondents were asked to mention some concerns associated with the adoption of cloud computing technologies in their libraries based on their experience. The qualitative responses to this item were sorted into similar topics, and similar issues were grouped for analysis. Out of the 116 respondents, 114 responded to the study (Table 7). Results presented in Table 7 show that the majority (111: 95.7%) of

the respondents are mostly concerned with the security & privacy of information or files stored in cloud computing technologies. Followed by 98 (84.5%) respondents who mentioned inadequate skills to use cloud computing technologies, 76 (65.5%) respondents cited lack of knowledge and awareness of cloud computing technologies, 66 (56.9%) respondents mentioned unstable Internet connectivity as a challenge to adopting cloud computing technologies, and more than half (61: 52.3%) of the respondents cited lack of policy on adoption of cloud computing technologies.

Table 7: Concerns related to cloud computing adoption mentioned by the respondents

Concerns related to cloud computing adoption are mentioned	No of respondents	Percentage
Security & privacy	111	95.7%
Skills to use cloud computing technologies	98	84.5%
Knowledge and awareness of cloud computing technologies	76	65.5%
Unstable internet connectivity	66	56.9%
Lack of policy on the adoption of cloud computing technologies	61	52.3%

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Discussion of findings

Cloud computing technologies used by librarians in Colleges of Education libraries in Nigeria.

Findings on the type of cloud computing technologies used by librarians in Colleges of Education libraries revealed that YouTube, Google Drive, OneDrive, Gmail, and Google Scholar are the most commonly used cloud computing technologies by the librarians in the selected Colleges of Education libraries in Nigeria. This shows that librarians in academic libraries use cloud computing technologies such as YouTube, Google Drive, OneDrive, Gmail, and Google Scholar. This finding is in line with the existing literature, especially the publications of Tripathi and Pandey (2019), Aiyebelin et al. (2020), and Njoku and Ken-Agbiriogun (2021) on the use of cloud computing technologies. The finding also agrees with the findings of Omwansa, Waema, and Omwenga (2014) that librarians in university libraries in South Africa are aware of and use cloud computing technologies.

Level of computer literacy skills to use cloud computing technologies.

The study revealed that almost half of the respondents rated their computer literacy skills to use cloud computing to be very good, followed by those who rated their computer skills to be excellent. This result is not surprising as librarians have been attending several workshops on skills development. There is no way the present librarian in this digital age can function excellently without the skills to use cloud computing technologies. Several studies have previously mentioned librarians' lack of computer skills to effectively operate in this digital era (Chisenga, 2012; Baro & Godfrey, 2015; Baro, Obaro & Aduba, 2019).

Purpose of using cloud computing technologies by the librarians in Colleges of Education.

The most commonly mentioned purpose of librarians using cloud computing technologies is to store and share files, share videos related to library orientations/other video content, and collaborate with other librarians for research projects. This shows that the librarians in university libraries in Colleges of Education libraries in Nigeria are using cloud computing technologies to store and share files, share videos related to library orientations/other video contents, and collaborate with other librarians for research projects. These findings are in line with the findings of the study by Aiyebelehin et al. (2020), which found that librarians in universities in Edo State, Nigeria, used cloud computing services and technologies for improved library services. Zubairu, Akiola and Hamzat (2021) studied “Awareness and Adoption of Cloud Computing in Nigerian Libraries: An Aid to Library Services”. The analysis showed areas in which cloud computing has been adopted in the various university libraries, including library management software (LMS), storage of data and files, backup/storage of information resources, data import and export, resource repository, cataloguing and classification, and acquisition. This may be why Arua, Ogbo, and Nwebiem (2020) recommended that libraries strive to utilise various Internet technologies to improve library and information service delivery.

The benefits of adopting cloud computing to render library services.

The study revealed that adopting cloud computing technologies has advantages such as storage capacity, access to files from anywhere, better performance, data security, software updates automatically, and lower maintenance costs. For example, Zhang et al. (2014) reported on the benefits that might be gained by applying cloud computing to libraries, such as overcoming low storage space limits, improving data transfer, and increasing the data transferring speed in addition to sharing knowledge. Using cloud computing in libraries is considered one of the most important modern approaches, which has been paid attention to as it represents one of the solutions suitable for developing libraries, overcoming financial and storage problems, elevating the level of service quality, and ameliorating outputs. Arkorful (2019) also studied cloud computing adoption in public and private universities in Sub-Saharan Africa and reported that the potential benefits associated with cloud computing include a reduction of total costs of acquisition or ownership (TCO) of hardware, software and skilled resources. The advent of cloud computing opens up a variety of options that can be employed in the care of data. For data stored on a physical device, such as a laptop, desktop computer, or mobile device, it is important to keep copies on one of the many cloud-based storage services such as Dropbox, OneDrive, Google Drive, and so on. This technique is easy and inexpensive.

Concerns associated with adopting cloud computing technologies.

Some of the concerns associated with adopting cloud computing technologies among librarians in colleges of education libraries in Nigeria are:

Security and privacy concerns

Among the concerns related to the adoption of cloud computing technologies in libraries mentioned by librarians in colleges of education libraries, security and privacy concerns were the most mentioned. This result strengthens the outcomes of several studies; for instance, a survey by Jalamneh and Khder (2021) identified challenges facing the application of cloud computing, including security and privacy, dependency (loss of control), lack of flexibility, and knowledge and integration. Netshakhuma (2023) assessed cyber security at South African universities. The results from the literature review revealed poor implementation and adherence to cyber security strategy and standards by employees and students; poor cyber security awareness relative to information communication technology (ICT) infrastructures and assets; and lack of strategy and framework to implement cyber security management. The study

recommends continuous monitoring and evaluation of information management systems at various South African universities to assess the state. The survey by Tella, Ukwoma and Kayode (2020) also found that perceived security and reliability were reported to exert the most significant influence on adoption. The study recommends, based on the findings, that academic libraries in Nigeria should make sure that the cloud providers do not compromise the security of the cloud computing they adopt. This may be why Earp et al. (2005) suggested that service providers' provision of robust security and privacy mechanisms would improve users' trust in the services, which manifested in the online sharing of personal information.

Skills to use cloud computing technologies

Skills to use cloud computing technologies was the second most mentioned concern by the librarians. No doubt, skills to use new technology are a major concern for librarians in developing countries. For example, Dhanushraja and Dhanushraja (2014) discussed the state of libraries in India. They reported that libraries are busy adopting cloud-based services for library users owing to the fact that libraries lack professionals with skills and knowledge in cloud computing technologies. This suggests that librarians must acquire new knowledge and make use of new technologies such as OneDrive to extend library service beyond the physical wall and keep users attracted to the library services in the shift of providing library services technologically. The study by Arkorful (2019) recommended that there is a need for training IT personnel and creating awareness of the benefits of cloud computing to enable institutions of higher learning to adopt them to enhance their productivity.

Knowledge and awareness of cloud computing technologies

The librarians mentioned the third most common concern related to knowledge and awareness of cloud computing technologies. This finding is consistent with the findings of Muhammad et al. (2017) and Sabiti, Sarika, and Bulu (2015), who, in their studies, reported the need to create awareness among librarians on the different cloud computing technologies and services they can be used for. The level of understanding of cloud computing technologies might differ from one institution to another depending on the level of awareness campaigns organised.

Unstable Internet connectivity

Unstable Internet connectivity was the fourth most mentioned concern by the librarians. Stable Internet connectivity is the bedrock of the use of modern technology in libraries. Therefore, using cloud computing technologies means having continuous connectivity. For example, the study by Agandi, Agandi and Gull (2013) confirms that the Internet has been a driving force in various technologies that have been developed, including cloud computing. The advent of the Internet has enabled libraries to practice resource sharing effectively, especially with functional digital libraries. According to Arua, Ogbo and Nwebiem (2020), "No one can think of providing effective modern library service without Internet facilities" (p.80).

Lack of policy on the adoption of cloud computing technologies

The lack of policy statements regarding the adoption of cloud computing technologies was the least mentioned concern by the librarians. This shows that they are not too bothered by having policy statements regarding the use of cloud computing technologies. University libraries must formulate policies regarding the use of emerging technologies such as cloud computing technologies, social media, IR development, and so on. This will help guide the effective deployment of such technologies to support rendering library services in this digital age.

Conclusion

The study investigated the level of awareness and use of cloud computing technologies by librarians in Colleges of Education libraries in Nigeria. Based on the analysis, the study found that YouTube, Google Drive, OneDrive, Gmail, and Google Scholar are the most common cloud computing technologies used by librarians in Colleges of Education libraries in the South-South region of Nigeria. It also emerged that librarians use cloud computing technologies to store and share files, share videos related to library orientations/other video contents, and collaborate with other librarians for research projects. The results show that adopting cloud computing technologies has advantages such as storage capacity, access to files from anywhere, better performance, data security, software updates automatically, and lower maintenance costs. The study identified concerns associated with adopting cloud computing technologies, such as security & privacy, skills to use cloud computing technologies, knowledge and awareness of cloud computing technologies, unstable Internet connectivity, and lack of policy on the adoption of cloud computing technologies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, several recommendations are made to enhance the deployment of cloud computing technologies in library services. Firstly, it is essential to provide continuous training and re-training for staff to effectively utilize cloud computing technologies. Before transitioning to a cloud computing environment, it is necessary to update all policies and current operational procedures to align with the new requirements. Additionally, it is important to specify the technical specifications for the cloud transition, identifying the suitability of the library's cloud computing software for both short-term and long-term use. Lastly, the library should carefully select a suitable computing service provider to ensure optimal performance and reliability. These recommendations aim to address the challenges and improve the effectiveness of cloud computing in library services.

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